

Single crystal structure refinement of $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{Br}_2$ and its surface affinity on titanium dioxide using PXRD, SEM and XRF measurements

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Abstract : $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{Br}_2]$, $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$ = quinoline, complex has been synthesized and the structure was refined by single crystal analysis. Complexation of quinoline moiety with Co^{II} was identified by spectral assignments. Structure of the title complex consists; Co atom is coordinated with two bromide ligands and two N atoms from two quinoline molecules. Single crystal refinement data viz. $M = 477.06$, $a = 8.7325(4) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 9.6233(4) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 11.1537(5) \text{ \AA}$, $\alpha = 80.483(3)^\circ$, $\beta = 73.548(4)^\circ$, $\gamma = 72.573(4)^\circ$, volume = $854.34(6) \text{ \AA}^3$, space group P-1 (no. 2), $Z = 2$ imply $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ (Q = quinoline) is symmetric with two fold rotation axis and belong to triclinic system. Surface affinity of the complex on TiO_2 is dependent upon the concentration of the co-solvent, 2-propanol. The cobalt(II) complex is bound with the solid surface as surface adsorbed species $\text{TiO}_2 : \text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2$, which is subsequently converted into $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{TiO}_2$ (surface species) due to surface chemistry however within thermodynamic limit. SEM images indicate the growth of particles is restricted due to Co^{II} deposition. XRF measurements characterize the surface species as implanted Co^{II} ion into TiO_2 lattice to generate $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{TiO}_2$ (surface species).

Keywords : Co^{II} -quinoline, X-ray diffraction, adsorption on anatase, XRF analysis, complex adsorption.

Introduction

Inorganic pharmacology is an important field with a number of transition metal complexes being needed in therapy as drugs¹. Quinoline is the backbone for most natural products, therefore, used for the design of many synthetic compounds having diverse pharmacological applications such as antibacterial, antifungal, immune suppressive, analgesic, vasorelaxing, antiplasmodial, anticancer, anticonvulsant and antihypertensive activities^{1,2}. For example, dynemicin-A and streptonigrin are naturally occurring members of the quinoline derived compounds belonging to the class of antitumor, antibiotics, antifungal³ agents. The 8-(diethylamino)hexylamino-6-methoxy-4-methyl-quinoline is highly effective against the protozoan parasite, similarly, its derivatives have reduced toxicity and superior therapeutic utility⁴⁻⁷. Further, both quinoline and its metal complexes find extensive relevance in chemical and biological fields.

Dipositive transition metal ions can coordinate with quinoline moiety to yield $\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{X}_2\text{Q}_2$ (Q = $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$) type of complexes. Metal complexes with quinoline and its derivatives have been found to possess potent phosphodi-

esterase inhibitory activity, HIV-1 integrase inhibitors and useful in the treatment^{8,9} of asthma. Cobalt(II) prefers four coordination with quinoline ligand leading to significance in geometry and molecular overall shape. The relatively low difference in crystal field stabilization energies between octahedral and tetrahedral cobalt(II) complexes is partly responsible for the formation of more tetrahedral complexes than that of any other transition metal ion. Generally, stabilities of the tetrahedral and the octahedral configurations are affected by the ligand properties, size, shape, polarizability and π -acceptor capacity. One of the most studied series¹⁰⁻¹² of complexes is $\text{Co}^{\text{II}}\text{L}_2\text{X}_2$ (where L = pyridine, pyrazines, hydrazines, quinoline and isoquinoline; X = Cl^- , Br^- , I^- , OCN^- or SeCN^-). Recently, the role of the cobalt/copper metals in photo-induced DNA cleavage reactions was reported by designing complex molecules having benzo[h]quinoline-macrocycles¹³ structure.

Cobalt is a common constituent in waste waters from nuclear processes. Therefore, it is important to retain and separate it from cobalt containing¹⁴ water sources. Hence, effective and simple methods should be explored for its

removal before disposing of the wastes in aquatic systems. Separation procedures based on adsorption phenomena are important in the analytical and radiochemistry of trace elements because of their simplicity, efficiency and selectivity. Cation adsorption onto oxide surfaces is a well-known phenomenon, and the adsorption of Co^{2+} ions onto various oxides (TiO_2 , SiO_2 , Al_2O_3 , MnO_2 , Fe_2O_3 , Fe_3O_4 , kaolinite, ZrO_2 and NiFe_2O_4) has been extensively^{15,16} studied. In addition, titanium dioxide (TiO_2) semiconductor has attracted a great deal of attention in environmental wastewater treatment in the past decade, because it generates highly oxidative hydroxyl free radicals ($\cdot\text{OH}$), which can degrade many toxic and non-biodegradable¹⁷ organics. Previous studies indicated that the photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 catalysts depended strongly on two factors: adsorption behavior and the separation efficiency¹⁷ of electron-hole pairs. The adsorption capacity can be generally improved by increasing the specific surface area of catalysts¹⁸⁻²¹ and the structural characteristics of the adsorbate metal complex. Pure titanium dioxide can function as photocatalyst by absorbing in the UV region for its activity²². Contrarily, incorporation of transition metal ions in the lattice of titania can improve the sensitivity of the catalyst, that is metal ion implanted catalyst can absorb visible light and becomes an efficient photocatalyst. Zhou *et al.*²³ reported that the particle size of TiO_2 has a strong influence on metal growth on the catalyst surface. Crystal structure of the complex can be an excellent model to define solid surface-complex interaction. Moreover, the rigidity of the geometry of the ligand surrounding the metal ion can have specific affinity towards semiconductor surface.

In the present study, quinoline type of ligand was chosen because it does not form hydrogen bonds with other ligand about the cobalt atom. Quinoline complexes and their structural properties are themselves of interest because some exhibit pharmacological applications. Second,

influence of structure of the complex with a semiconductor metal oxide like TiO_2 is promising in waste water treatment. Moreover, metal implanted semiconductors are useful as efficient catalyst and in advanced electronics. Therefore, single crystal refinement and surface affinity of the metal complex on metal oxide particles were undertaken.

Experimental

Materials and methods:

$\text{CoBr}_2 \cdot x\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99%), spectral grade KBr and anatase TiO_2 (BET surface area = 150–200 m^2/g , particle size = ~ 50 nm and micropore volume = ~ 0.027 cm^3 g^{-1}) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich and used as received. Isopropanol, quinoline (AR) and all other chemicals were purchased from Himedia and SD Fine Chemicals (India). Ethanol was purified by repeated distillations over CaO. All other solvents were distilled before use and water was triply distilled over alkaline potassium permanganate in an all glass apparatus.

Elemental analyses were performed on an Elementar Vario EL III-Germany instrument. The FT-IR spectral investigations in the range 4000–400 cm^{-1} were carried out on a Thermo Nicolet-6700 FT-IR instrument (KBr pellet method). The crystalline powders were mixed with KBr in a 1% (w/w) mixture and pressed into pellet at 10 ton pressure for 8 min. This was to obtain a transparent pellet, which was inserted into the apparatus to record vibrational spectrum in the range 4000 to 400 cm^{-1} with a resolution 1 cm^{-1} . Electronic absorption spectral studies were undertaken on a double beam spectrophotometer (Shimadzu model 2450, Japan) with integrating sphere attachment (ISR-2200) and thermostated cell holder using quartz cells. Cobalt(II) complex was 3.332×10^{-4} – 6.664×10^{-5} M in neat water or in distilled DMSO solvent. Single crystal of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ was isolated from deionized water preheated to 70 °C. X-Ray fluorescence (XRF) measurements were made on a Bruker S4-Pioneer instrument. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) patterns were recorded in the range of $2\theta = 10$ –70° by step scanning using 2θ increments of 0.02° and a fixed counting time of 5 sec/step with X'PERT diffractometer employing $\text{Cu-K}\alpha$ radiation; the wavelength of the X-ray source was $\lambda = 1.541$ Å. The acceleration voltage was 50 kV with 40 mA current. The morphology of the samples

was investigated by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Hitachi, Model : S-3400N), acceleration voltage 0.3 kV to 30 kV. Adsorption experiments were carried out in Technico cooling water bath shaker at room temperature using modified Fuerstenau²⁴ method.

Crystallographic data collection and refinement :

A crystal of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex with size 0.24 mm \times 0.17 mm \times 0.11 mm was mounted on an Oxford Diffraction Xcalibur diffractometer with an Eos (Nova) detector consists ω and ϕ scan mode in the range of $2.00^\circ < \theta < 25.00^\circ$. All diffraction measurements were performed at 293(2) K using graphite monochromated Mo-K α radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$). A total of 6848 reflections were measured. The structure was solved by direct methods and refinement by full-matrix least squares on F^2 using 32-bit Olex2-1.1 version program. Hydrogen atoms were located from difference Fourier syntheses and included in the structure factor calculations with a riding model.

Data collection : CrysAlis PRO (Oxford Diffraction, 2009); cell refinement : CrysAlis PRO; data reduction : CrysAlis PRO; absorption correction : multi-scan (CrysAlis PRO), programs were used to solve structure and used to refine structure : 32-bit Olex2-1.1 version (Oleg Dolomanov and Horst Puchmann, Durham University, UK), molecular graphics : ORTEP-3 for windows-version 2.02 (University of Glasgow, 2008); software used to prepare material for publication : 32-bit Olex2-1.1 version.

Synthesis of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{Br}_2]$:

Dibromobis(quinoline-N)cobalt(II) was prepared¹⁰ by the reported method. Hydrated cobalt(II) bromide (1 g) was dissolved in 10 mL of distilled ethanol and refluxed with quinoline (2.5 mL) for 3–4 h. Bluish violet color complex precipitated was filtered, washed with hot ethanol subsequently with dry ether. The crude sample was recrystallized by dissolving in 5–10 mL of deionized water preheated to 70 °C; acidified with few drops of conc. HBr. The solution was kept overnight in dark at room temperature; dark blue colored crystals separated out were filtered, washed with ethanol and dry ether. Yield : 0.792 g, 79%. IR spectral data : Complex (free quinoline) (KBr, cm^{-1}) : ν (CC/CN) 1593(s) (1593) $[\text{B}_{1u}]$; ν (CC) 1508(s) (1493) $[\text{B}_{2u}]$; ν (CC/CN), δ (CCC/NCC) 1459(s)

(1444) $[\text{B}_{3u}]$; ν (CC) δ_{1p} (CH) 1389(m) (1388) $[\text{A}_g]$; ν (CC/CN) 1313(s) (1314) $[\text{B}_{2u}]$; ν (CC) δ_{1p} (CH) 1226(m) (1222) $[\text{B}_{1u}, \text{B}_{2u}]$; ν (CC/CN), δ_{1p} (CH) 1133(m) (1131) $[\text{B}_{3g}]$; ν (CC) δ (CCC) 1050(w) (1024) $[\text{A}_g]$; ν (Co-N) 432(s). Electronic absorption spectral data : λ_{max} nm; ϵ_{max} $\text{M}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$; neat water (in DMSO) : 277; 7956 (275; 11059), 299; 7430 (300; 7578), 312; 7683 (314; 7473), 509; 100 (537; 243), (674; 243). Elemental analysis data : Found : C, 44.05; H, 2.53; N, 5.32; Br, 32.98. Calcd. : C, 45.31; H, 2.95; N, 5.87; Br, 33.49%.

Adsorption studies :

About 0.1 g ($2.6201 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$) of the complex $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{Br}_2]$ was taken in a 125 mL stoppered bottle. The complex was dissolved in neat water or in water/5–30% (w/w) 2-propanol mixed solvents and maintaining ionic strength with NaNO_3 (1 M). Then polycrystalline TiO_2 (200 mg) was added to the above solution and the entire solution was placed in a Technico cooling water bath shaker at different time intervals such as 0, 30, 60, 90, 120 and 300 min at 300 K. After definite time intervals the filtrate solutions were centrifuged and both the solid and solution were to instrumental analysis. The adsorbent (TiO_2) was removed by filtration through 0.45 μm Whatman filter paper at various time intervals and dried over vacuum to understand the surface affinity of the complex ion. PXRD and scanning electron microscopic analysis (SEM) were made on the dried solid samples obtained from adsorption experiments. The amount of cobalt adsorbed onto the adsorbent TiO_2 was determined by XRF.

Results and discussion

Quinoline reacts with CoBr_2 in ethanol under controlled distillation to give cobalt(II) complex : $\text{CoBr}_2 + \text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N} \rightarrow \text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2$ (where Q = $\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N}$). Dibromobis(quinoline-N)cobalt(II) is microcrystalline violet-blue colored solid, stable at room temperature, soluble in neat water and easily soluble in pure DMSO. Elemental analysis finds the complex consists of ligand to metal ratio 1 : 1 with formula $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$. The complex was characterized and structural assignment made using IR, UV-Vis and single crystal X-ray diffraction refinement.

FTIR and electronic absorption spectral analysis :

Infrared spectral analysis was employed to study the coordination of quinoline ligand with the cobalt(II) center. Therefore, IR spectrum of the complex was com-

pared with that of free ligand to determine the changes in vibrational modes that might have taken place due to coordination. $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{C}_9\text{H}_7\text{N})_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex shows intense metal-ligand stretching vibrational band in addition to aromatic vibrational modes for the organic moiety. The band in the region at $\sim 432(\text{s}) \text{ cm}^{-1}$ has been assigned to a $\nu(\text{Co-N})$ (quinoline-N) stretching vibration and the 337 cm^{-1} band to $\nu(\text{Co-Br})$ bond. Such assignment can be made in comparison with the infrared spectra ($400\text{--}140 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) of the complexes $[\text{M}^{\text{II}}\text{Q}_2\text{X}_2]$ ($\text{M} = \text{Co}, \text{Ni}, \text{Cu}$ or Zn ; $\text{Q} = \text{quinoline}$ or $\text{quinoline-}d_7$; $\text{X} = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{I}$ or NCS) as detailed^{25–27}. Quinoline ring vibrations occur in the region $1050\text{--}1593 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, which parallel with an investigation²⁶ on liquid quinoline in the region $1000\text{--}1700 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ has strong bands in the $3600\text{--}3000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $1670\text{--}1600 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ region, signifying the presence of lattice water. In cobalt(II)-quinoline-N complex the $\nu(\text{CC/CN})$, $\delta(\text{CCC/NCC})$ $1459(\text{s})$ (1444 cm^{-1} B_{3u}) is found shifted to higher energy 15 cm^{-1} than that observed in free ligand. The $\nu(\text{NCC})$ is not a pure vibration in complex but is coupled with the aromatic ring vibrations of the quinoline ring. In the FT-IR spectra of the Co^{II} complex, the vibration modes due to various $\nu(\text{CC/CN})$, $\delta(\text{CCC/NCC})$, $\nu(\text{CC/CN})$ and $\nu(\text{CC/CN})$ $\delta_{1p}(\text{CH})$ of free quinoline ligand are seen to be shifted due to complexation with Co^{II} central metal ion.

The UV-Vis spectra of the complex in neat water and in pure DMSO display three absorption peaks at 277, 299, 312 nm (water) and 275, 300, 314 nm (DMSO) with very high $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = \sim 7430\text{--}11059 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ values, which can be assigned to the $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ intra-ligand transitions²⁷ of quinoline. Cobalt(II) complex shows less intense bands at *ca.* 500–680 nm assigned to *d-d* transitions of the metal ions. The ground state for a Co^{II} ion in T_d symmetry is 4A_2 , hence, the possible transitions are; $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^4T_1(P)$, $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^2E(G)$ and $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^2T_1(G)$. However, $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ shows less number of bands in the electronic spectra with absorption maxima^{28,29} at 509 (water)/537 nm (DMSO) due to $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^2T_1$ and at 674 nm (DMSO) due to $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^4T_1(P)$; while $^4A_2 \rightarrow ^2E$ transition is obscured. Electronic spectra of the complex infers that the *d-d* transitions are weak with low molar extinction coefficient values $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 100\text{--}243 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$, such *d-d* spectrum is distinctive only in tetrahedral environment.

Single crystal X-ray diffraction refinement :

The single crystal X-ray structure of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex is remarkable as shown in Fig. 1. The structure consists of two independent neutral molecules and the

Fig. 1. ORTEP structure of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex showing the atom-numbering scheme and displacement ellipsoids.

contacts between them are indicative of hydrophobic interactions. The quinoline moiety coordinated to the cobalt(II) center are non-planar. ORTEP structure of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ is presented in Fig. 1. The crystal structure of the compound consists of discrete neutral $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ molecules, lying on a two-fold axis. The asymmetric unit consists of one metal center, two quinoline ligands and two Br^- anions. Central metal atom is surrounded by two N atoms from two quinoline ligands and two Br^- anions to attain distorted tetrahedral coordinated geometry. The packing diagram of the title compound is presented in Fig. 2. Crystal data and structure refinement of the complex, $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$, are as listed in Table 1. All other related data such as; atomic coordinates, isotropic dis-

Fig. 2. Packing diagram of the $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex.

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_2\text{CoBr}_2$
Formula weight	477.06
Temperature (K)	293(2)
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	P-1
a (Å), b (Å), c (Å)	8.7325(4), 9.6233(4), 11.1537(5)
α° , β° , γ°	80.483(3), 73.548(4), 72.573(4)
Volume (Å ³)	854.34(6)
Z	2
ρ_{calc} (mg mm ⁻³)	2.782
μ (mm ⁻¹)	8.521
$F(000)$	699
Crystal size (mm)	0.24 × 0.17 × 0.11
Theta range for data collection	2.76 to 29.09°
Index ranges	-11 ≤ h ≤ 11, -12 ≤ k ≤ 12, -14 ≤ l ≤ 14
Reflections collected	6848
Independent reflections	3918 [$R(\text{int}) = 0.0238$]
Data/restraints/parameters	3918/0/208
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.008
Final R indexes [$I > 2\sigma(I)$]	$R_1 = 0.0685$, $wR_2 = 0.2053$
Final R indexes [all data]	$R_1 = 0.1096$, $wR_2 = 0.2215$
Largest diff. peak/hole (e Å ⁻³)	2.014/-1.613

placement parameters and anisotropic displacement parameters are presented as supplementary information (Tables S1-S4). The Co atom is coordinated by two bromide ligands and two N atoms from two quinoline groups

Table S1. Atomic coordinates (Å × 10⁴) and equivalent isotropic displacement parameters (Å² × 10³) for $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$. U_{eq} is defined as 1/3 of the trace of the orthogonalised U_{ij} tensor

Atom	x	y	z	U_{eq}
Co1	4074.8(12)	8039.2(9)	2037.2(8)	20.3(3)
Br1	3082.5(14)	6537.6(10)	3779.1(9)	55.7(4)
Br2	2063.0(15)	9400.6(12)	987.2(11)	66.8(4)
N2	5895(7)	6709(6)	757(5)	20.4(12)
N1	5007(7)	9469(6)	2604(5)	22.7(12)
C18	7098(8)	5546(7)	1082(6)	18.8(13)
C17	8021(8)	4478(7)	254(6)	20.0(14)
C9	4033(9)	10484(7)	3410(6)	23.8(15)
C10	5708(9)	6856(8)	-393(6)	28.7(16)
C16	7412(9)	5416(8)	2291(6)	26.8(15)
C15	8628(10)	4254(8)	2610(7)	32.3(17)
C8	4695(11)	11476(7)	3815(7)	32.2(19)
C14	9545(10)	3180(8)	1800(7)	31.3(17)

C13	9245(9)	3269(8)	665(7)	29.6(16)
C12	7731(9)	4637(8)	-929(7)	29.4(16)
C1	6576(10)	9405(9)	2188(8)	35.6(18)
C11	6576(10)	5822(8)	-1274(6)	29.4(16)
C7	2277(10)	10587(8)	3893(7)	32.1(17)
C2	7321(12)	10349(11)	2514(10)	52(3)
C4	3558(14)	12528(9)	4634(7)	45(2)
C3	6343(13)	11371(9)	3347(9)	47(2)
C6	1326(12)	11646(9)	4664(8)	46(2)
C5	2002(15)	12603(9)	5028(8)	50(2)

Table S2. Anisotropic displacement parameters (Å² × 10³) for $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$. Anisotropic displacement factor exponent : $-2p^2[h^2a^*2U_{11} + \dots + 2hka \times b \times U_{12}]$

Atom	U_{11}	U_{22}	U_{33}	U_{23}	U_{13}	U_{12}
Co1	20.5(5)	16.0(5)	21.1(5)	-4.9(3)	-5.6(4)	2.2(4)
Br1	61.2(7)	49.3(6)	47.9(6)	-4.4(4)	-0.6(5)	-13.9(5)
Br2	63.6(8)	61.8(7)	67.7(7)	-16.1(5)	-29.3(6)	11.7(5)
N2	20(3)	17(3)	22(3)	-4(2)	-7(2)	1(2)
N1	24(3)	23(3)	22(3)	3(2)	-6(2)	-7(3)
C18	19(3)	17(3)	20(3)	-3(3)	-3(3)	-5(3)
C17	16(3)	16(3)	25(3)	-8(3)	1(3)	-3(3)
C9	36(4)	19(3)	22(3)	1(3)	-16(3)	-7(3)
C10	29(4)	28(4)	21(3)	-2(3)	-6(3)	3(3)
C16	31(4)	25(4)	22(3)	-4(3)	-7(3)	-2(3)
C15	33(5)	30(4)	34(4)	5(3)	-15(4)	-6(3)
C8	57(6)	22(4)	28(4)	9(3)	-27(4)	-16(4)
C14	25(4)	28(4)	40(4)	0(3)	-11(3)	-5(3)
C13	27(4)	21(4)	39(4)	-5(3)	-5(3)	-5(3)
C12	28(4)	25(4)	30(4)	-13(3)	3(3)	-3(3)
C1	35(5)	32(4)	37(4)	9(3)	-9(4)	-12(4)
C11	32(4)	32(4)	19(3)	-1(3)	-7(3)	-2(3)
C7	36(5)	25(4)	34(4)	-13(3)	-11(3)	2(3)
C2	35(5)	59(6)	66(6)	20(5)	-18(5)	-27(5)
C4	89(8)	33(4)	28(4)	-4(3)	-28(5)	-23(5)
C3	64(7)	42(5)	50(5)	8(4)	-24(5)	-34(5)
C6	52(6)	38(5)	36(5)	-14(4)	-5(4)	4(4)
C5	77(8)	33(5)	36(5)	-12(4)	-15(5)	-3(5)

in a distorted tetrahedral³⁰ arrangement. The N1-Co1-N2, N2-Co1-Br1, N2-Co1-Br2 and Br2-Co1-Br2 bond angles are; 111.1 (2), 108.02 (15), 106.52 (15) and 111.78 (6)° respectively and other selected bond angles are as present in Table 2. The bond lengths of Co1-N2 and Co1-N1 viz. 2.075 (6) and 2.051 (5) Å respectively, likewise, the bond lengths of Co1-Br1 and Co1-Br2 are; 2.3413 (13) and 2.3353 (13) Å respectively. The small

Table S3. Bond angle (deg) and bond lengths (Å) of the [Co^{II}(Q)₂Br₂] complex

C18-C17-C13	118.2(6)	C3-C2-C1	118.2(8)
C17-C18-C16	119.5(6)	C6-C7-C9	118.8(7)
C10-N2-C18	118.1(6)	C5-C4-C8	123.0(8)
C16-C15-C14	121.9(7)	C17-C13	1.436(10)
C15-C16-C18	119.2(7)	C17-C12	1.388(10)
C8-C9-C7	118.1(7)	C9-C8	1.439(9)
C8-C3-C2	120.6(8)	C10-C11	1.408(10)
C14-C13-C17	121.4(7)	C16-C15	1.370(10)
C13-C14-C15	119.8(7)	C15-C14	1.388(11)
C12-C17-C18	118.9(6)	C8-C4	1.426(12)
C12-C17-C13	122.9(6)	C8-C3	1.363(13)
C12-C11-C10	117.5(7)	C14-C13	1.348(11)
C11-C12-C17	120.2(6)	C12-C11	1.361(10)
C7-C6-C5	121.7(9)	C1-C2	1.406(12)
C4-C8-C9	117.2(8)	C7-C6	1.359(10)
C4-C5-C6	121.2(9)	C2-C3	1.382(14)
C3-C8-C9	117.4(8)	C4-C5	1.288(14)
C3-C8-C4	125.3(8)	C6-C5	1.396(13)

Table S4. Hydrogen atom coordinates (Å × 10⁴) and isotropic displacement parameters (Å² × 10³) of the [Co^{II}(Q)₂Br₂] complex

Atom	x	y	z	U _{eq}
H8	4957	7693	-636	34
H14	6799	6113	2855	32
H13	8846	4182	3390	39
H12	10363	2402	2041	38
H11	9844	2532	137	35
H10	8329	3931	-1487	35
H1	7241	8697	1647	43
H9	6369	5944	-2064	35
H7	1813	9941	3678	39
H2	8440	10288	2178	62
H4	3959	13189	4895	54
H3	6813	11994	3590	56
H6	195	11735	4957	55
H5	1317	13308	5565	60

variations in the Co1-N1 (2.051) and Co1-N2 (2.075) Å bond lengths between metal and quinoline ligands characterize the geometrical flexibility of the coordination surroundings. Solvate molecules are not located between the largest of metal complex moieties. In a layer of the crystal, every molecule [Co^{II}(Q)₂Br₂] is surrounded by four other mutually symmetrically related molecules. Other selected bond lengths are presented in Table 2, which are

Table 2. Selected bond angles (deg) and bond lengths (Å) of the [Co^{II}(Q)₂Br₂] complex

Br2-Co1-Br1	113.78(6)	C10-N2-Co1	117.1(5)
N2-Co1-Br1	108.02(15)	C1-N1-Co1	119.5(5)
N2-Co1-Br2	106.52(15)	C1-N1-C9	118.8(6)
N2-C18-C17	121.1(6)	Co1-Br1	2.3413(13)
N2-C18-C16	119.4(6)	Co1-Br2	2.3353(13)
N2-C10-C11	123.9(7)	Co1-N2	2.075(6)
N1-Co1-Br1	109.37(16)	Co1-N1	2.051(5)
N1-Co1-Br2	108.08(16)	N2-C18	1.365(8)
N1-Co1-N2	111.1(2)	N2-C10	1.317(8)
N1-C9-C8	121.6(7)	N1-C9	1.358(9)
N1-C9-C7	120.3(6)	N1-C1	1.303(10)
N1-C1-C6	123.4(8)	C18-C17	1.399(9)
C18-N2-Co1	123.8(4)	C18-C16	1.429(9)
C9-N1-Co1	121.8(5)	C9-C7	1.452(11)

in good agreement with those found in similar reported cobalt complexes^{27,31-33}. The molecular geometry within the quinoline ligand is normal^{34,35}. Hydrogen atom coordinates and isotropic displacement parameters for [Co^{II}(Q)₂Br₂] complex are presented as supplementary information (Table S4). The single crystal refinement of the cobalt(II) complex implies and confirms the triclinic form of the crystal and the geometry of the complex is distorted tetrahedral.

Adsorption of complex ion on anatase :

To understand the affinity of the neutral cobalt(II) complex on the surface of titanium dioxide, adsorption study was carried out in neat water and in water/2-propanol mixed solvents. The complex binding was followed spectrally at various time intervals. Fig. 3 is a repetitive scan spectra illustrating the extent of cobalt(II) complex uptake by anatase-TiO₂ in 20% (w/w) aqueous/2-propanol system at definite time intervals. It was observed that λ_{max} at 509 nm is decreased indicating the surface adherence of cobalt(II) complex on anatase-TiO₂. However, Fig. 3 implies that the extent of adsorption is very high initially and after definite time interval, a decreasing trend was observed. As can be seen in Fig. 3, the maximum absorption shifted from 509 to 498 nm with a decrease in the concentration of complex. When the complex concentrations are considered, it disappeared slowly from 0 to 300 min time interval and no new product or intermediate product causing absorption in the near UV region was observed. The rate of adsorption relates to the prob-

Fig. 3. Repetitive scan spectra recorded for the $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex adsorption on polycrystalline TiO_2 in water + $\text{Pr}^{\text{I}}\text{OH}$ (80/20% (w/w)) mixed solvent at various time intervals : (a) 0, (b) 30, (c) 60, (d) 90, (e) 120 and (f) 300 min respectively. Complex concentration = $2.62 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, ionic strength = 1 M NaNO_3 , $\text{pH} = 6.96$ and at 300 K .

ability of OH radicals, reacting with the complex molecules, hence, a significant amount of shift in the absorption maximum. The various surface reactions are presented in eqs. (1) and (2);

Surface complex adduct :

Surface species :

It is also found that the quantum of adsorption is dependent upon the composition of the mixed solvent (water/2-propanol mixtures = 100/0 to 70/30% (w/w)). The metal complex was found to be adsorbed on the surface as the concentration of the alcohol is increased. This indicates the surface affinity of the neutral complex when the hydrophobicity of the mixed solvent is enhanced by increasing the concentration of 2-propanol. This probably is due to the neutral metal complex interaction with the $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}$ - tail of co-solvent (2-propanol). The complex chemisorbs nondissociatively and the tetrahedral plane of the molecule essentially favors for the surface affinity and coverage. In addition, the ionic interactions of ligand with the Ti-O and Ti-OH groups of titania would induce a preferential adsorption of the molecule to the surface. To investigate the effect of pore structure and adsorption abilities of anatase, a set of N_2 adsorption-desorption iso-

therms measurement was carried out. The hysteresis loop, which is a special feature of isotherm, was believed to be related with pore channels and modulation of channel structure. However, no characteristic feature was observed, subsequently, indicate the presence of mesoporosity. This prominent improvement in the adsorption capacity might be attributed to the fact that the porous structure of the polycrystalline- TiO_2 particles is suitable for the accommodation of complex molecules which helps their entrapment therein by taking advantage of the very large surface area inside the pore. In the case of cobalt(II) complex, it is a kind of spheroid, which can readily be entrapped into the pore of the polycrystalline- TiO_2 particles, in addition to the electrostatic interaction between the TiO_2 surface inside the pore and the complex itself, and, therefore, more molecules tend to be retained inside the porous structure. In a very recent investigation, Anbalagan has reported¹⁷ the formation of photoinduced metal ion implantation of cobalt in the lattice of anatase. The surface chemistry plays an important role on the adsorbed species. That is surface adsorbed species $\text{TiO}_2 : \text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2$ is converted into an adduct of the type $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{TiO}_2$ (surface species). The surface species is nothing but the penetration of the surface generated Co^{II} ion into the lattice of TiO_2 . Therefore, the surface species; $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{TiO}_2$ was subjected to PXRD and surface micro-structure analysis.

Powder X-ray diffraction analysis of $\text{TiO}_2 : \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ species :

Pure anatase and isolated surface adsorbed species $\text{TiO}_2 : \text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2$ obtained at different time intervals were analyzed for their crystal structures. Anatase crystals showed extremely high crystalline-phase stability, retaining the pure phase of anatase even after adsorption of the complex upto 300 min time interval of adsorption. The PXRD patterns of both the samples basically belong to anatase form, therefore, cobalt(II) complex is chemically bonded either through surface species or through strong metal-supported interaction³⁶. Both pure form of TiO_2 and surface species; $\text{Co}^{\text{II}} : \text{TiO}_2$ exhibit patterns (Fig. 4) characteristic of anatase crystal phase (JCPDS file numbers 01-071-1166, 00-002-0387). The polycrystalline anatase structure was confirmed by (101), (004), (200), (105) and (211) diffraction peaks. The XRD patterns of anatase have a main peak at $2\theta = 25.2^\circ$ corres-

Fig. 4. PXRD diffraction patterns of the polycrystalline TiO_2 semiconductor particles collected from adsorption of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ on TiO_2 in neat water and at various time intervals : (a) pure TiO_2 , and from the mixture, (b) 0 min, (c) 30 min, (d) 60 min, (e) 90 min, (f) 120 min, (g) 300 min respectively. Medium : 1 M NaNO_3 at 300 K.

ponding to the (101) plane (JCPDS 21-1272), which confirms the phase purity of the crystalline solid. This suggests that the crystals do not contain impurity phase like rutile, hence transformation of crystal phase has not occurred. Therefore, rutile and other form of the crystal such as brookite phase³⁷ have not been detected. Similarly, the PXRD patterns inferred the absence of metallic cobalt and oxides of cobalt. The shape of diffractive peaks of the crystal planes in $\text{TiO}_2 : \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ (surface species) closely resemble³⁸ to that of the pure TiO_2 . However, Co^{II} adhered to the surface of the adsorbent as $\text{TiO}_2 : \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ (surface species) cannot be eliminated, therefore, this was verified using scanning electron microscopic and X-ray fluorescence analyses.

Scanning electron microscopic analysis :

The SEM images of $\text{TiO}_2 : \text{Co}^{\text{II}}$ (surface species) particles are presented in Fig. 5, which, reveals that the particle surface is relatively rough and apparently built from tiny particles. It can be seen that the particles are spherical³⁹ with various size distributions. The particles have open porous structures, probably due to the surface implantation of the Co^{II} ion. The cobalt(II) complex surface implanted particles are found to be highly agglomerated and some are non-spherical in characteristics. These differences in morphology, particle shape and size indicate the presence of surface : Co^{II} species. From SEM images, it can be presumed that cobalt-deposited titania

Fig. 5. XRF spectra of the adduct, $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]/\text{TiO}_2$, isolated from adsorption of Co^{II} complex on TiO_2 at various contact time in neat water : (a) 0, (b) 60, (c) 120 and (d) 300 min respectively at 300 K. The inset shows the respective SEM images.

samples consist of very fine free individual grains plus other granular aggregates : very large distributions of shape and dimensions of the particles were observed⁴⁰, with average diameter of 160 nm. It is evident that the growth of particle is highly restricted due to Co^{II} deposition, which is of significant importance not only for the design of surface properties, but also for tuning the electronic structure of the semiconductor.

XRF measurement of Co loaded titania :

Surface concentration of Co^{II} on TiO_2 was calculated from X-ray fluorescence studies. XRF spectra are shown in Fig. 5 and Table 3 presents the concentration of cobalt loaded on the solid with respect to different time intervals. Table 3 exhibits the relationship between density of Co^{II} in atomic percent (*at. %*) with respect to time, in which Co is enhanced from 0.179 to 0.194%. XRF analysis shows the presence of titanium and oxygen in the TiO_2 sample at 0 min contact time in adsorption study, however, presence^{41,42} of a small quantity of cobalt was evident from the samples isolated at 30, 60, 90, 120 and 300 min contact time intervals. Fig. 5 compares the XRF spectra for pure TiO_2 and complex adsorbed anatase (Co -

Table 3. XRF analysis of $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ adsorbed on anatase- TiO_2 in neat water and 70/30% (w/w) : water/ $\text{Pr}^{\text{i}}\text{OH}$ systems at various contact time intervals, medium : 1 M NaNO_3

Contact time (min)	Atomic concentration (%)			
	Neat water		Water/ $\text{Pr}^{\text{i}}\text{OH}$	
	Ti (Net int.)	Co (Net int.)	Ti (Net int.)	Co (Net int.)
0	59.489 (4942)	0	59.374 (4950)	0
30	59.370 (4925)	0.119 (16.46)	59.200 (4936)	0.174 (24.32)
60	59.370 (4961)	0.159 (22.13)	59.300 (4934)	0.177 (24.64)
90	59.380 (4951)	0.162 (22.59)	59.350 (4914)	0.186 (25.72)
120	59.410 (4995)	0.161 (22.54)	59.490 (3581)	0.194 (19.44)
300	59.360 (5000)	0.179 (25.15)	59.490 (3581)	0.194 (19.44)

TiO_2). According to the calibration curve the atomic content of cobalt is varying from 0.179 to 0.194%. Two prominent peaks are observed, in which, the high intensity peak is due to primary X-rays, and the other one is due to secondary X-rays. The high intensity peak at 4.5 keV ($k\alpha$) and secondary peak at 4.9 keV ($k\beta$) indicate titanium, and the peaks at 6.9 ($k\alpha$) and 7.65 keV ($k\beta$) are attributed^{17,43} to cobalt. The net intensity (Table 3) of prominent Co peak is found to increase from 16.46 (kCps) to 25.72 (kCps); it appears that the rise in dopant density aids to produce respective states in TiO_2 . The X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy confirmed the existence of cobalt atoms in the TiO_2 powder. The initially formed surface : complex adduct has become surface species such as; Co^{II} : TiO_2 . It could evidence that the cobalt atoms were introduced into the TiO_2 lattice.

Conclusion :

Dipositive cobalt combines with quinoline ligand and yields stable, crystalline solid with tetrahedral geometry. Complexation of the quinoline moiety with Co^{II} was identified using IR, and electronic spectra. Electronic spectral measurement in neat water and in pure DMSO of the $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ complex illustrates weak *d-d* transitions with low ϵ values. The structure of the complex has been established by single crystal X-ray diffraction refinement and confirmed to be triclinic crystal form with distorted tetrahedral geometry. $[\text{Co}^{\text{II}}(\text{Q})_2\text{Br}_2]$ is preferably adsorbed on the solid surface forming surface : complex adduct, simultaneously it becomes converted into surface species; TiO_2 : Co^{II} due to thermodynamically controlled surface chemistry. The surface species was identified by XRF measurement, which infers the implantation of Co in the lattice of TiO_2 . SEM images support the restriction of

agglomeration of particles due to Co^{II} penetration into the lattice. In this investigation, it has been found that metal complex surface interaction leads to the formation of surface species that can be identified by PXRD, SEM and XRF analysis. Metal loaded semiconductor solids find applications as catalysts and in advanced electronics.

Supplementary data

Crystallographic data for the structural analysis have been deposited with the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre Number, CCDC No. 784126. Copies of this information can be had free of charge from The Director, CCDC, 12 Union Road, Cambridge, CB2 1EZ, UK (Fax : 44-1223-336033; E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk or <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk>) on request quoting the deposition number.

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